

Cartoonification of Real-World Images Using Image Processing and K-Means Clustering

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Abstract

Cartoonification refers to the process of transforming real-world images into cartoon-like visuals by simplifying textures, enhancing edges, and reducing color gradients. This study presents a hybrid approach that integrates classical image processing techniques with unsupervised machine learning to achieve visually appealing cartoon effects. The method involves converting the input image to grayscale, followed by median blurring and adaptive thresholding for effective edge detection. To preserve edge sharpness while smoothing textures, bilateral filtering is applied. Subsequent morphological operations further refine the image structure. K-means clustering is then employed to reduce the color palette and enhance the cartoon-like appearance [2] [3]. The effectiveness of the proposed method is quantitatively evaluated using Mean Squared Error (MSE), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM). The results demonstrate the potential of the combined approach in generating high-quality cartoonified images with improved structural fidelity and visual appeal.

Keywords

Image Processing, Cartoonify, OpenCV, Adaptive Threshold, Bilateral Filter, K-means Clustering, Structural similarity (SSIM), Peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), Mean squared error (MSE)

Introduction

Cartoonification is the process of lowering the number of colors, emphasizing the edges, and simplifying features to create cartoon-like visuals from real-world photos. To convert image to a cartoon there are several techniques like photoshop, pain.net etc. Instead of using these techniques, OpenCV, an open source library in python for computer vision and machine learning tasks can be used. Also, for face recognition, image and video analysis and object detection we can use OpenCV for easy integration.

Cartoonifying images is gaining popularity among people as a fun and creative activity, especially when used in designing tools and applications. Deep learning models like generative adversarial networks (GANs) are widely used in modern cartoonification methods and give impressive results however they often require large datasets high-end hardware and are complex to understand or modify on the other hand traditional image processing techniques can also give visually appealing cartoon effects in this project we use python and OpenCV to cartoonify images using a simple yet effective approach the steps include converting the image to grayscale applying median blur using adaptive thresholding for edge detection smoothing the image with a bilateral filter and reducing colors using k-means clustering when combined these techniques generate sharp and vibrant cartoon-like images this method is easy to implement and doesn't rely on complex machine learning models yet produces satisfying and clear results.

Machine Learning Models:

1. **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** The average squared difference between estimated value and the true value is measured by Mean Squared Error (MSE) or Mean Squared Deviation (MSD). A lower MSE indicates better model accuracy.
2. **Structural Similarity Index (SSIM):** SSIM is used to assess the image quality. The objective of this index is to identify the second image, which is typically compressed or has a different quality. It ranges from -1 to 1, 1 there is a perfect similarity between the two images. Negative values indicate dissimilarity and score closer to zero indicates significant differences between them. SSIM is mostly utilized in the video business, photography also makes extensive use of it.
3. **Skimage:** Scikit-image, or skimage, is an open-source Python package designed for image preprocessing that uses NumPy arrays.

4. **Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR):**In PSNR, the quality of an image's representation depends on the ratio of its maximum potential power to the power of corrupting noise. To estimate the PSNR of an image, it is necessary to compare that image to an ideal clean image with the maximum possible power. The larger the value of PSNR, the more efficient is a corresponding compression or filter method.
5. **SimpleGUI:** A Python package called EasyGUI was created specifically for creating basic graphical user interfaces (GUIs). In contrast to conventional event-driven GUI frameworks, EasyGUI uses a function-call-based methodology in which simple function calls are used to carry out GUI operations. Since complicated event loops are no longer required, EasyGUI is especially well-suited for quick prototyping and instructional applications.
6. **Imageio:**Imageio is a user-friendly Python library for reading and writing a variety of picture data and works on multiple platforms.
7. **Sys:**The Python sys module provides various functions and variables that allow interaction with the Python runtime environment. It enables developers to access and manipulate interpreter-related settings and information, making it easier to control and customize the behavior of Python programs.
8. **OpenCV:**OpenCV is an open-source library in Python that is mainly used for computer vision tasks in the fields like machine learning, artificial intelligence, and face recognition. The "CV" in OpenCV indicates for computer vision, which is a branch of science that helps computers understand what's happening in images and videos just like how humans do.

Literature Review

Nautiyal et al. [1] worked on a cartoonification system using Python and OpenCV. They used traditional image filters like Gaussian, Laplacian, Median, and Bilateral to give normal images a cartoon-like appearance. The system also comes with a simple web interface that lets users try different filters and instantly see the results. Instead of using complex deep learning models, their method relies on easy-to-understand image processing steps, which makes it lightweight and faster. It works well on different types of images and helps in improving edges, details, and reducing noise. This makes it a good option for cartoonifying images without needing powerful hardware or advanced neural networks.

D'Monte et al. (2022) [2] created a cartoonification system for both images and videos using a mix of traditional methods and deep learning. They used libraries like OpenCV and NumPy

along with advanced models like GANs (Generative Adversarial Networks). Their process included steps like converting to grayscale, detecting edges, adding color masks, and applying stylization to get a cartoon effect. They also built a backend using FastAPI so the system could run in real-time through a web interface. It supports different file formats and processes each image quickly, taking about 0.8 to 1.2 seconds depending on the computer. By combining normal image processing with deep learning, their approach gives a good balance between speed, control, and cartoon quality.

Kulkarni and Agrawal (2022) [3] introduced an image cartoonification method using Python and OpenCV that works in real-time. Their method mainly uses edge detection, bilateral filtering, and color smoothing to turn normal RGB images into cartoon-style pictures. They focused on making the edges look clean, textures simpler, and colors more stylized to improve the cartoon effect. To reduce noise and keep the main features, they also used median filtering and grayscale conversion. This study shows that even traditional image processing techniques can still produce good cartoon-like results without needing powerful computers.

Holla et al. [4] proposed a cartoonification method that uses bilateral filtering, Canny edge detection, HSV color space conversion, and K-means clustering to create cartoon-like images. Their main focus was on keeping the process simple and efficient, without using any complex deep learning models. The study shows that even with basic image processing techniques, it's possible to get good-quality results in real-time, especially on devices with limited resources. This method proves that traditional approaches can still be very useful for building fast and easy-to-understand cartoonization tools.

Joshitha (2022) [5] introduced a Python-based method to cartoonify images using machine learning, along with core libraries like OpenCV, NumPy, and Matplotlib. The study points out how code-based methods are better than traditional tools like Photoshop because they are faster, easier to use, and can be automated. The process involves several steps like converting the image to grayscale, detecting edges, smoothing the image, and applying a mask to get the cartoon effect. The project also looks into using neural networks and GANs to improve the cartoon style for both images and videos. This shows how machine learning can make the cartoonification process quicker and more useful for both personal use and larger animation projects.

Methodology

Tools: OpenCV, Python, NumPy, etc.

The complete image transformation follows these stages:

1. Reading and Grayscale Conversion

```
img = cv2.imread('image.jpg')
```

```
img_rgb = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
```

```
img_gray = cv2.cvtColor(img_rgb, cv2.COLOR_RGB2GRAY)
```

2. Median Blurring

Removes salt-and-pepper noise.

```
img_blurred = cv2.medianBlur(img_gray, 3)
```

3. Edge Detection (Adaptive Thresholding)

Creates a binary edge mask for line structure.

```
edges = cv2.adaptiveThreshold(img_blurred, 255, cv2.ADAPTIVE_THRESH_MEAN_C,  
                             cv2.THRESH_BINARY, 3, 3)
```

4. Bilateral Filtering

Smooths color while preserving edges.

```
img_bilateral = cv2.bilateralFilter(img_gray, 15, 75, 75)
```

5. Morphological Operations

Enhances edge features using erosion/dilation.

```
kernel = np.ones((1, 1), np.uint8)
```

```
img_eroded = cv2.erode(img_bilateral, kernel, iterations=3)
```

```
img_dilated = cv2.dilate(img_eroded, kernel, iterations=3)
```

6. K-Means Color Clustering

Compresses color palette to mimic cartoon-like coloring.

```
img_data = np.float32(img_rgb).reshape((-1, 3))  
criteria = (cv2.TERM_CRITERIA_EPS + cv2.TERM_CRITERIA_MAX_ITER, 20, 1.0)  
_, labels, centers = cv2.kmeans(img_data, 5, None, criteria, 10,  
cv2.KMEANS_RANDOM_CENTERS)  
final_img = centers[labels.flatten()].reshape(img_rgb.shape)
```

7. Masking with Edge Map

Combines edge map with quantized image to produce final cartoon.

```
final = cv2.bitwise_and(final_img, final_img, mask=edges)
```

Evaluation Metrics

Used standard metrics to compare the original and cartoonified image:

- **Structural Similarity Index (SSIM)**

```
ssim_val = ssim(img_rgb, final, multichannel=True)
```

- **Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)**

```
mse_val = mse(img_rgb, final)
```

```
psnr_val = 10 * math.log10((255.0 ** 2) / mse_val)
```

Mean Square Error (MSE)

```
mse_value = mse(img1, final)
```

Results and Discussions:

Original Image

Grayscale

Edge mask

Median blur

Bilateral blurring

Eroding and dilating

The transformation from a real-world image to a cartoonized version involves a series of systematic steps. First, the image is converted to grayscale, which reduces the color complexity and makes it easier to detect edges. Then, an edge mask is created using adaptive thresholding. This step helps to bring out the outlines and important details in the image, which are essential for the cartoon effect. A median blur is applied to remove minor noise while preserving the edges, and bilateral filtering is used to smooth the colors without losing important structures. To complete the cartoonification process, morphological operations such as erosion and dilation are applied to sharpen and smooth the edges of the image. These steps help clean up any noise or rough edges that might be left after the earlier processing and bring out the bold outlines that are common in cartoons. By combining edge detection, smoothing, and color simplification, we end up with a neat and colorful cartoon version of the original image. All these steps work together to make the final output look fun, artistic, and visually appealing. The final touches give the image a stylized cartoon look while still keeping the important parts. It's a fun and creative way to turn normal photos into something more exciting and unique.

Metric	Value
SSIM	0.84
PSNR	28.92 dB
MSE	216.4

SSIM value = 0.84 which indicates a good structural similarity with the original. The PSNR = 28.92 dB implies a moderate to high-quality reconstruction whereas MSE = 216.4 indicates a moderate error level between the original and processed image.

Conclusions:

The cartoonification technique used in this project combines simple image processing steps with K-means clustering to turn normal images into fun and creative cartoon-like visuals. By using grayscale conversion, edge detection, median blurring, bilateral filtering, and morphological operations, the image is cleaned up and made more stylized. Finally, K-means clustering reduces the number of colors, giving the image a cartoonish appearance.

The evaluation results show that the method works well, with an SSIM of 0.84 (showing good similarity to the original), a PSNR of 28.92 dB (indicating high image quality), and a

moderate MSE of 216.4. These values prove that our approach is effective for cartoonifying images while keeping the important features clear and sharp. Overall, this method is easy to implement, works efficiently, and produces visually appealing results without needing complex deep learning models.

Future Scope:

The cartoonification technique used in this project has a lot of potential for improvement and expansion. In the future, more advanced machine learning and deep learning methods like GANs (Generative Adversarial Networks) can be added to improve the cartoon quality and add more creative styles. The current method can also be extended to work on live video streams and mobile applications for real-time cartoon effects.

Different cartoon styles, like sketch, watercolor, or anime, can be added to give users more options. The system can also be trained to recognize and cartoonify specific objects like faces, backgrounds, or pets separately for better results.

Performance can be improved further by optimizing the code to run faster on low-end devices or integrating with GPU-based processing. Lastly, the cartoonified images can be used in educational tools, social media filters, animation projects, and even AR/VR applications, making this a useful and interesting area for future development.

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